

[white paper]

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Theorems in Topology

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Abstract

This is an introductory collection of theorems in topology.

keywords: axioms, definitions, theorems, topology

The most updated version of this white paper is available at

<https://osf.io/zm56w/download>

<https://zenodo.org/record/6205551>

Introduction

1. We present some basic theorems in Topology using the fewest number of mathematical symbols, without losing information.
2. The idea is to provide a *global overview* of the *results* without worrying about their proofs.
3. This white paper is being *updated from time to time*.

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Metalinguistic Symbols

4. A metalinguistic symbol is not part of the language.
5. The symbol $:=$ means that *what is on the left side is defined by the right side of it*.
6. Depending on the context, \equiv and \neq are used to state a theorem.
7. For example, in the statement of a theorem, \equiv can be read as *is, are, has, have* etc.
8. [1, 2]

Archimedean Property

9. Theorem

$$(\forall x \in F \exists n \in \mathbb{N} : n > x) \equiv (F \text{ has the Archimedean Property})$$

10. $F :=$ ordered field

11. (9) means that \mathbb{N} is *unbounded* in F .

12. Theorem

$$\mathbb{Q}, \mathbb{R} \equiv \text{Archimedean Property}$$

13. $\mathbb{Q} :=$ set of rational numbers

14. $\mathbb{R} :=$ set of real numbers

15. [3]

Density Theorem

16. Theorem

$$(x, y \in \mathbb{R}, x < y) \rightarrow (\exists q \in \mathbb{Q} : x < q < y)$$

17.

\mathbb{Q} is dense in \mathbb{R}

18. [3]

Open Interval

19. Definition

$$(a, b) = \{x \in X \mid a < x < b\}$$

20. $(a, b) :=$ open interval in X

21. $X :=$ set

22. [3]

Open Set

23. Definition

$$(\forall x \in X : x \in (a, b) \subseteq X) \equiv X := \text{open set in } \mathbb{R}$$

24. Definition

$X := \text{open set in } Y$ if

(i) $X \subseteq Y$

(ii) $\forall x \in X : x \in (a, b) \subseteq X$

25. $X, Y := \text{sets}$

26. $(a, b) := \text{open interval in } \mathbb{R}$

27. [3]

Open Interval, Open in \mathbb{R}

28. Theorem

$$\forall (a, b) : (a, b) \equiv \text{open set in } \mathbb{R}$$

29. Theorem

$$(\forall h. h := \text{half-open interval in } \mathbb{R}) \rightarrow (h \not\equiv \text{open set in } \mathbb{R})$$

30. Theorem

$$(\forall c. c := \text{closed interval in } \mathbb{R}) \rightarrow (c \not\equiv \text{open set in } \mathbb{R})$$

31. $(a, b) := \text{open interval in } \mathbb{R}$

32. [3]

Infinite Interval, Open in \mathbb{R}

33. Theorem

$$a \in \mathbb{R} \rightarrow (a, \infty) \equiv \text{open in } \mathbb{R}$$

34. Theorem

$$b \in \mathbb{R} \rightarrow (-\infty, b) \equiv \text{open in } \mathbb{R}$$

35. $(a, \infty), (-\infty, b) :=$ infinite open intervals in \mathbb{R}

36. [3]

Empty Set, Set of Real Numbers, Open in \mathbb{R}

37. Theorem

$$\emptyset, \mathbb{R} \equiv \text{open in } \mathbb{R}$$

38. [3]

Open Subset of \mathbb{R} , Open in \mathbb{R}

39. Theorem

$$(X \equiv \text{open in } \mathbb{R}) \leftrightarrow (\forall x \in X, \exists c > 0, c \in \mathbb{R} : (x - c, x + c) \subseteq X)$$

40. $X \subseteq \mathbb{R}$; $(x - c, x + c) :=$ open interval in \mathbb{R}

41. [3]

Union of Open Sets in \mathbb{R}

42. Theorem

$$A \cup B \equiv \text{open in } \mathbb{R}$$

43. $A, B :=$ open sets in \mathbb{R}

44. [3]

Union of a collection of sets

45. Definition

$\bigcup X :=$ union of all elements of X

46. $\bigcup X := \{y \mid \exists Y \in X, y \in Y\}$

47. $X :=$ collection of sets

48. $Y :=$ set

49. [3]

Intersection of a collection of sets

50. Definition

$\bigcap X :=$ intersection of all elements of X

51. $\bigcap X := \{y \mid \forall Y \in X, y \in Y\}$

52. $X :=$ collection of sets

53. $Y :=$ set

54. [3]

Union of Open Subsets of \mathbb{R} , Open in \mathbb{R}

55. Theorem

$$\bigcup X \equiv \text{open in } \mathbb{R}$$

56. $X :=$ set of open subsets of \mathbb{R}

57. $\bigcup X :=$ union of all elements of X

58. [3]

Upper/Lower Bound in \mathbb{R}

59. Definition

$$(\exists m \in \mathbb{R} : \forall s \in S, s \leq m) \equiv (m := \text{upper bound of } S)$$

60. Definition

$$(\exists k \in \mathbb{R} : \forall s \in S, s \geq k) \equiv (k := \text{lower bound of } S)$$

61. $\emptyset \neq S \subseteq \mathbb{R}$

62. [4]

Bounded Set

63. Definition

`bounded set := bounded above and below`

64. [3]

Bounded Open Intervals

65. Theorem

$$(\forall X \subseteq \mathbb{R}, X \neq \emptyset, X := \text{open set in } \mathbb{R}) \rightarrow (X = \bigcup B)$$

66. $B :=$ set of all bounded open intervals in X

67. $\bigcup B :=$ union of all elements of B

68. [3]

Pairwise Disjoint Open Intervals

69. Theorem

$$(\forall X \subseteq \mathbb{R}, X \neq \emptyset, X := \text{open set in } \mathbb{R}) \rightarrow (X = \bigcup_c P)$$

70. \bigcup_c := countable union

71. P := set of pairwise disjoint open intervals

72. [3]

Modal operators

73. Definitions

74. $\Box, \Diamond :=$ (unary) modal operators

75. $\Box :=$ *necessarily*

76. $\Diamond :=$ *possibly*

77. $\varphi :=$ formula

78. $\Diamond\varphi \equiv \neg\Box\neg\varphi$

79. [5]

Intersection of Open Sets in \mathbb{R}

80. Theorem

$$A \cap B \equiv \text{open in } \mathbb{R}$$

81. Theorem

$$\bigcap_{i=1}^n A_i \equiv \text{open in } \mathbb{R}$$

82. Theorem

$$\bigcap_{i=1}^{\infty} A_i \equiv \neg \square \text{ open in } \mathbb{R}$$

83. $A, B, A_i :=$ open sets in \mathbb{R}

84. $\bigcap A_i :=$ arbitrary intersection of A_i

85. $\neg \square :=$ not necessarily

86. [3]

Closed Set in \mathbb{R} , Complement of a Set

87. Definition

$$(\mathbb{R} \setminus X \equiv \text{open in } \mathbb{R}) \rightarrow (X := \text{closed in } \mathbb{R})$$

88. $X \subseteq \mathbb{R}$

89. $\mathbb{R} \setminus X :=$ complement of X in \mathbb{R}

90. [3]

Intersection of Closed Sets

91. Theorem

$$A \cap B \equiv \text{closed in } \mathbb{R}$$

92. $A, B :=$ closed sets in \mathbb{R}

93. [3]

Accumulation Point of a Set in \mathbb{R}

94. Definition

$(\mathbb{R} \ni x := \text{accumulation point of } S \leftrightarrow$
 $\leftrightarrow \forall a, b \in \mathbb{R} (a < x < b \rightarrow \exists y \in S (a < y < b \wedge y \neq x)))$
 $\equiv \text{every open interval containing } x \text{ contains at least one point of } S$
 $\text{different from } x$

95. $S \subseteq \mathbb{R}$

96. $(\mathbb{R} \ni x) \equiv (x \in \mathbb{R})$

97. [3]

Closed in \mathbb{R} , Accumulation Points

98. Theorem

$$(C \equiv \text{closed in } \mathbb{R}) \leftrightarrow (x \equiv \text{accumulation point of } C \rightarrow x \in C)$$

99. $C \subseteq \mathbb{R}$

100. [3]

Closure of a Set in \mathbb{R} , Intersection

101. Definition

$$S \subseteq \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \bar{S} := \bigcap \{C \mid S \subseteq C, C \equiv \text{closed in } \mathbb{R}\}$$

102. $\bar{S} :=$ closure of S in \mathbb{R}

103. $\bar{S} :=$ *intersection of all closed sets in \mathbb{R} containing S*

104. Theorem

$$\bar{S} \equiv \text{closed in } \mathbb{R}$$

105. [3]

Closure, Accumulation Point, Closed in \mathbb{R}

106. Theorems

107.

$$S \subseteq \bar{S}$$

108.

$$(C \equiv \text{closed in } \mathbb{R}, S \subseteq C) \rightarrow (\bar{S} \subseteq C)$$

109.

$$\bar{S} = S \cup \{x \in \mathbb{R} \mid x \equiv \text{accumulation point of } S\}$$

110.

$$(S \equiv \text{closed in } \mathbb{R}) \leftrightarrow (S = \bar{S})$$

111.

$$(x \in \bar{S}) \leftrightarrow \forall X (x \in X \rightarrow \exists s \in X)$$

112. $s \in S \subseteq \mathbb{R}$

113. $\bar{S} :=$ closure of S in \mathbb{R}

114. $X :=$ open interval

115. [3]

Open Disk in \mathbb{C} , Neighborhood

116. Definition

$$N_r(c) := \{z \in \mathbb{C} : |z - c| < r\}$$

117. $N_r(c) := r$ -neighborhood of c (open disk in \mathbb{C})

118. $c :=$ center of the open disk

119. $r :=$ radius of the open disk

120. [3]

Open in \mathbb{C}

121. Definition

$$(\forall z \in X \exists D : z \in D \subseteq X) \rightarrow (X := \text{open in } \mathbb{C})$$

122. Theorem

$$(X \equiv \text{open in } \mathbb{C}) \leftrightarrow (\forall w \in X \exists d > 0 : N_d(w) \subseteq X)$$

123. $w \in X \subseteq \mathbb{C}; \quad d \in \mathbb{R}$

124. $D :=$ open disk

125. $N_d(w) :=$ open disk in \mathbb{C} (d -neighborhood of w)

126. [3]

Closed in \mathbb{C}

127. Definition

$$(\mathbb{C} \setminus X \equiv \text{open in } \mathbb{C}) \rightarrow (X \equiv \text{closed in } \mathbb{C})$$

128. $X \subseteq \mathbb{C}$

129. $\mathbb{C} \setminus X :=$ complement of X in \mathbb{C}

130. [3]

Accumulation Point of a Set in \mathbb{C}

131. Definition

$(\mathbb{C} \ni z \equiv \text{accumulation point of } S \leftrightarrow$
 $\leftrightarrow \forall a \in \mathbb{C} \forall r \in \mathbb{R}^+ (z \in N_r(a) \rightarrow \exists w \in S (w \in N_r(a) \wedge w \neq z)))$
 $\equiv \text{every open disk containing } z \text{ contains at least one point of } S$
 $\text{different from } z$

132. $S \subseteq \mathbb{C}$

133. $(\mathbb{C} \ni z) \equiv (z \in \mathbb{C})$

134. $N_r(a) :=$ open disk in \mathbb{C} (r -neighborhood of a)

135. [3]

Closed in \mathbb{C} , Accumulation Points

136. Theorem

$$(C \equiv \text{closed in } \mathbb{C}) \leftrightarrow (\forall z \in \mathbb{C} : z \in C)$$

137. $C \subseteq \mathbb{C}$

138. $z :=$ accumulation point of C

139. [3]

Closure, Accumulation Point, Closed in \mathbb{C}

140. Theorems

141.

$$S \subseteq \bar{S}$$

142.

$$(C \equiv \text{closed in } \mathbb{C}, S \subseteq C) \rightarrow (\bar{S} \subseteq C)$$

143.

$$\bar{S} = S \cup \{z \in \mathbb{C} \mid z \equiv \text{accumulation point of } S\}$$

144.

$$(S \equiv \text{closed in } \mathbb{C}) \leftrightarrow (S = \bar{S})$$

145.

$$(z \in \bar{S}) \leftrightarrow \forall D (z \in D \wedge \exists s \in D)$$

146. $s \in S \subseteq \mathbb{C}$

147. $\bar{S} :=$ closure of S in \mathbb{C}

148. $D :=$ open disk in \mathbb{C}

149. [3]

Euclidean space

150. Definition

$$\mathbb{R}^n := \{(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) \mid x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n \in \mathbb{R}\}$$

151. $x, y \in \mathbb{R}^n; \quad k \in \mathbb{R}$

152. $x + y = (x_1 + y_1, x_2 + y_2, \dots, x_n + y_n)$

153. $kx = (kx_1, kx_2, \dots, kx_n)$

154. $-x = (-x_1, -x_2, \dots, -x_n)$

155. $x - y := x + (-y) = (x_1 - y_1, x_2 - y_2, \dots, x_n - y_n)$

156. $|x| = \sqrt{x_1^2 + x_2^2 + \dots + x_n^2}$

157. $|x| :=$ norm (length/magnitude) of x

158. $\mathbb{R}^n := n$ -dimensional Euclidean space

159. [3]

Unitary space

160. Definition

$$\mathbb{C}^n := \{(z_1, z_2, \dots, z_n) \mid z_1, z_2, \dots, z_n \in \mathbb{C}\}$$

161. $\mathbb{C}^n := n$ -dimensional unitary space
(with the definitions of *sum*, *scalar multiple*, and *norm*)

162. [3]

Generalized Triangle Inequality

163. Theorem

$$|x + y| \leq |x| + |y|$$

164. $x, y \in \mathbb{R}^n$ (or $x, y \in \mathbb{C}^n$)

165. $|x| :=$ norm of x

166. [3]

Open Ball in \mathbb{R}^n , Neighborhood

167. Definition

$$B_d(a) := \{y \in \mathbb{R}^n : |y - a| < d\}$$

168. $B_d(a) :=$ open ball in \mathbb{R}^n (center a , radius d)
(d -neighborhood of $a \in \mathbb{R}^n$)

169. [3]

Open in \mathbb{R}^n , Open Ball in \mathbb{R}^n

170. Definition

$$(\forall x \in X \exists B : x \in B, B \subseteq X) \rightarrow (X := \text{open in } \mathbb{R}^n)$$

171. Definition

$$(\mathbb{R}^n \setminus X \equiv \text{open in } \mathbb{R}^n) \rightarrow (X := \text{closed in } \mathbb{R}^n)$$

172. $\mathbb{R}^n \setminus X :=$ complement of X in \mathbb{R}^n

173. $X \subseteq \mathbb{R}^n$; $B :=$ open ball in \mathbb{R}^n

174. [3]

Accumulation Point of a Set in \mathbb{R}^n

175. Definition

$$\forall B \subseteq \mathbb{R}^n (x \in B, \exists s \in B, s \neq x) \rightarrow \\ \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n \ni x := \text{accumulation point of } S \text{ in } \mathbb{R}^n$$

176. $S \subseteq \mathbb{R}^n$

177. $B :=$ open ball in \mathbb{R}^n ; $s \in S$; $(\mathbb{R}^n \ni x) \equiv (x \in \mathbb{R}^n)$

178. [3]

Closure of a Set in \mathbb{R}^n , Intersection

179. Definition

$$S \subseteq \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \bar{S} = \bigcap \{C \mid S \subseteq C \wedge C \equiv \text{closed in } \mathbb{R}^n\}$$

180. $\bar{S} :=$ closure of S in \mathbb{R}^n

181. $\bar{S} :=$ *intersection of all closed sets in \mathbb{R}^n containing S*

182. [3]

Open, Closed, Union, Intersection, Accumulation Point, Open Ball

183. Theorems

184.

$$(X \equiv \text{open in } \mathbb{R}^n) \leftrightarrow (\forall x \in \mathbb{R}^n \exists d > 0 : B_d(x) \subseteq X)$$

185.

$$\emptyset, \mathbb{R}^n \equiv \text{open and closed in } \mathbb{R}^n$$

186.

$$\bigcup A_i \equiv \text{open in } \mathbb{R}^n$$

187.

$$\bigcap_{i=1}^n A_i \equiv \text{open in } \mathbb{R}^n$$

188.

$$\bigcap K_i \equiv \text{closed in } \mathbb{R}^n$$

189.

$$\bigcup_{i=1}^n K_i \equiv \text{closed in } \mathbb{R}^n$$

190.

$$(C \equiv \text{closed in } \mathbb{R}^n) \leftrightarrow (\forall y \in \mathbb{R}^n : y \in C)$$

191.

$$S \subseteq \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow S \subseteq \bar{S}$$

192.

$$(C \equiv \text{closed in } \mathbb{R}^n, S \subseteq C) \rightarrow (\bar{S} \subseteq C)$$

193.

$$(S \subseteq \mathbb{R}^n) \rightarrow (\bar{S} = S \cup \{x \in \mathbb{R}^n \mid x \equiv \text{accumulation point of } S\})$$

194. $(S \equiv \text{closed in } \mathbb{R}^n) \leftrightarrow (S = \overline{S})$
195. $(x \in \overline{S}) \leftrightarrow \forall B (x \in B, \exists s \in B)$
196. $x \in \mathbb{R}^n$
197. $B_d(x) :=$ open ball (center x , radius d)
198. $A_i :=$ open sets in \mathbb{R}^n ; $i \in \mathbb{N} = \{1, 2, 3, \dots\}$
199. $\cup A_i :=$ union of all A_i
200. $K_i :=$ closed sets in \mathbb{R}^n
201. $\cap K_i :=$ intersection of all K_i
202. $C \subseteq \mathbb{R}^n$
203. $y :=$ accumulation point of R^n
204. $\overline{S} :=$ closure of S in \mathbb{R}^n
205. $B :=$ open ball
206. $s \in S$
207. [3]

Topology on S

208. Definition

$\mathcal{T} :=$ topology on S if

(i) $\emptyset, S \in \mathcal{T}$

(ii) $X \subseteq \mathcal{T} \rightarrow \bigcup X \in \mathcal{T}$

(iii) $(Y \subseteq \mathcal{T} \wedge Y := \text{finite}) \rightarrow \bigcap Y \in \mathcal{T}$

209. (208.ii) means that \mathcal{T} is closed under taking arbitrary unions.

210. (208.iii) means that \mathcal{T} is closed under taking finite intersections.

211. $S :=$ set

212. $\mathcal{T}, X, Y :=$ sets of sets

213. $\mathcal{P}(S) :=$ power set of S (set of all subsets of S)

214. Theorem

$$\mathcal{T} \subseteq \mathcal{P}(S) \in \mathcal{P}(\mathcal{P}(S))$$

215. [3]

Trivial Topology

216. Definition

$$\mathcal{T} := \{\emptyset, S\}$$

217. $\mathcal{T} :=$ trivial topology (or indiscrete topology) on S

218. $S :=$ set

219. [3]

Discrete Topology

220. Definition

$$\mathcal{P}(S)$$

221. $\mathcal{P}(S) :=$ power set $:=$ discrete topology

222. $S :=$ set

223. [3]

Topological Space

224. Definition

$(S, \mathcal{T}) :=$ topological space

225. $S :=$ set

226. $\mathcal{T} :=$ topology on S

227. [3]

Topology of a singleton

228. Definition

$$\mathcal{T} := \{\emptyset, \{a\}\}$$

229. $S = \{a\}$

230. $\mathcal{T} :=$ unique topology on S

231. [3]

Topologies of a set with two elements

232. Theorems

$$\mathcal{T}_1 = \{\emptyset, \{a, b\}\}$$

$$\mathcal{T}_2 = \{\emptyset, \{a\}, \{a, b\}\}$$

$$\mathcal{T}_3 = \{\emptyset, \{b\}, \{a, b\}\}$$

$$\mathcal{T}_4 = \{\emptyset, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}\}$$

233. $S = \{a, b\}$

234. $\mathcal{T}_i :=$ topologies on S

235. [3]

Coarser, finer, and incomparable topologies

236. Definition

$$\mathcal{T}_1 \subseteq \mathcal{T}_2$$

237. \mathcal{T}_1 is coarser than \mathcal{T}_2

238. \mathcal{T}_2 is finer than \mathcal{T}_1

239. incomparable := neither *finer* nor *coarser*

240. [3]

Standard topology on \mathbb{R}

241. Definition

$$\mathcal{T} := \{X \subseteq \mathbb{R} \mid \forall x \in X \exists a, b \in \mathbb{R} (x \in (a, b) \wedge (a, b) \subseteq X)\}$$

242. $\mathcal{T} :=$ standard topology on \mathbb{R}

243. $(a, b) :=$ open interval

244. [3]

Standard topology on \mathbb{C}

245. Definition

$$\mathcal{T} = \{X \subseteq \mathbb{C} \mid \forall z \in X \exists a \in \mathbb{C} \exists r \in \mathbb{R}^+ (z \in N_r(a) \wedge N_r(a) \subseteq X)\}$$

246. $N_r(a) = \{z \in \mathbb{C} : |z - a| < r\} :=$ open ball

247. $\mathcal{T} :=$ standard topology on \mathbb{C}

248. [3]

Standard topology on \mathbb{R}^n

249. Definition

$$\mathcal{T} = \{X \subseteq \mathbb{R}^n \mid \forall x \in X \exists a \in \mathbb{R}^n \exists r \in \mathbb{R}^+(x \in B_r(a) \wedge B_r(a) \subseteq X)\}$$

250. $B_r(a) = \{x \in \mathbb{R}^n : |x - a| < r\} :=$ open ball

251. $\mathcal{T} :=$ standard topology on the Euclidean space \mathbb{R}^n

252. [3]

Topological Space, Neighborhood

253. Definition

$$(U \in \mathcal{T}, x \in U) \equiv (U := \text{neighborhood of } x)$$

254. $(S, \mathcal{T}) :=$ topological space

255. [3]

Accumulation Point of a Set

256. Definition

$$(S \ni x \equiv \text{accumulation point of } A \leftrightarrow \\ \leftrightarrow \forall U \in \mathcal{T} (x \in U \rightarrow \exists y \in A (y \in U, y \neq x)))$$

257. $(S, \mathcal{T}) :=$ topological space

258. $A \subseteq S$

259. $(S \ni x) \equiv (x \in S)$

260. [3]

Closed, Accumulation Points, Topological Space

261. Theorem

$$(C \equiv \text{closed in } S) \leftrightarrow \forall x \in S (x \in C)$$

262. $(S, \mathcal{T}) :=$ topological space

263. $C \subseteq S$

264. $x :=$ accumulation points of C

265. [3]

Closure, Topological Space

266. Definition

$$A \subseteq S \rightarrow \bar{A} := \bigcap \{C \mid A \subseteq C, C \text{ is closed in } S\}$$

267. Theorem

$$\bar{A} \text{ is closed in } S$$

268. $(S, \mathcal{T}) :=$ topological space

269. $\bar{A} :=$ closure of A in S

270. $\bar{A} :=$ intersection of all closed sets in S

271. [3]

Topological Space, Closed, Accumulation Point

272. Theorems

273.

$$A \subseteq \bar{A}$$

274.

$$(C \equiv \text{closed in } S, A \subseteq C) \rightarrow (\bar{A} \subseteq C)$$

275.

$$\bar{A} = A \cup \{x \in S \mid x \equiv \text{accumulation point of } A\}$$

276.

$$(A \equiv \text{closed in } S) \leftrightarrow (A = \bar{A})$$

277.

$$(x \in \bar{A}) \leftrightarrow \forall O \subseteq S (x \in O, \exists y \in O, y \in A)$$

278. $(S, \mathcal{T}) :=$ topological space

279. $A \subseteq S$

280. $\bar{A} :=$ closure of A in S

281. $O :=$ open set

282. [3]

Bases

283. Definition

$$(S, \mathcal{T}) := \text{topological space} \rightarrow \\ \rightarrow \mathcal{B} \subseteq \mathcal{T} : \forall x \in \mathcal{T} \left(x = \bigcup_i B_i \right)$$

284. *Every element of the topology can be written as a union of elements from the basis.*

285. $\mathcal{B} :=$ basis for the topology \mathcal{T}

286. $B_i \in \mathcal{B}$

287. $\bigcup B_i :=$ arbitrary union

288. $\mathcal{T} :=$ generated by \mathcal{B} (or \mathcal{B} generates \mathcal{T})

289. [3]

Cover, Intersection Containment Property

290. Definition

$$(\forall x \in S \exists A \in \mathcal{X}(x \in A)) \rightarrow (\mathcal{X} \text{ covers } S)$$

291. Definition

\mathcal{X} has the intersection containment property on S
if

$$\forall x \in S \forall A, B \in \mathcal{X}(x \in A \cap B \rightarrow \exists C \in \mathcal{X}(x \in C, C \subseteq A \cap B))$$

292. $S, A, B, C :=$ sets; $\mathcal{X} :=$ set of sets

293. [3]

Basis, Cover, Intersection Containment Property

294. Theorem

$\mathcal{B} \equiv$ basis for a topology on S

\iff

\mathcal{B} covers S ,

\mathcal{B} has the intersection containment property on S

295. $S \neq \emptyset$

296. $\mathcal{B} :=$ collection of subsets of S

297. [3]

Subbasis

298. Theorem

$\mathcal{X} = \{(-\infty, b) \mid b \in \mathbb{R}\} \cup \{(a, \infty) \mid a \in \mathbb{R}\} \neq$ basis for a topology on \mathbb{R}

299. Theorem

$\mathcal{B} :=$ collection of all finite intersections of sets in $\mathcal{X} \rightarrow$
 $\rightarrow \mathcal{B}$ forms a basis for \mathbb{R} (because \mathcal{X} covers \mathbb{R}) \rightarrow
 $\rightarrow \mathcal{X} \equiv$ subbasis for the topology generated by \mathcal{B}

300. standard topology on $\mathbb{R} \rightsquigarrow$ generated by \mathcal{B}

301. [3]

Basis, Subbasis, Union

302. Theorem

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{X} := \text{set of sets} \rightarrow \\ \rightarrow & (\mathcal{X} \equiv \neg \square \text{ basis for } \mathcal{T}) \wedge \\ & \wedge (\mathcal{X} \equiv \text{subbasis for } \mathcal{T}_{\cup x}) \end{aligned}$$

303. $\neg \square$:= not necessarily

304. \mathcal{T} := topology on \mathbb{R}

305. $\mathcal{T}_{\cup x}$:= topology on $\cup \mathcal{X}$

306. $\cup \mathcal{X}$:= union of all elements of \mathcal{X}

307. [3]

Basis, Intersection, Subspace Topology

308. Theorem

$(S, \mathcal{T}) \equiv$ topological space with basis \mathcal{B} , $A \subseteq S \rightarrow$
 $\rightarrow \mathcal{B}_A = \{U \cap A \mid U \in \mathcal{B}\} \equiv$ basis for a topology \mathcal{T}_A on A

309. $\mathcal{T} :=$ subspace topology relative to A

310. [3]

Topological Space, Subset, Intersection

311. Theorem

$$(S, \mathcal{T}) \equiv \text{topological space, } A \subseteq S \rightarrow \mathcal{T}_A = \{U \cap A \mid U \in \mathcal{T}\}$$

312. $\mathcal{T}_A :=$ topology on A

313. [3]

Product Topology (basis, Cartesian product)

314. Definition

$$S_1 \times S_2 := \{(x, y) \mid x \in S_1, y \in S_2\}$$

315. Theorem

$$\begin{aligned} (\mathcal{T}_1 := \text{topology on } S_1, \mathcal{T}_2 := \text{topology on } S_2) &\rightarrow \\ \rightarrow \mathcal{B} = \{U \times V \mid U \in \mathcal{T}_1, V \in \mathcal{T}_2\} &\equiv \text{basis for } \mathcal{T} \end{aligned}$$

316. $\mathcal{T} :=$ product topology on $S_1 \times S_2$

317. [3]

Product Topology, Basis, Cartesian Product

318. Theorem

$$\begin{aligned} & (\mathcal{T}_1 := \text{topology on } S_1 \text{ with basis } \mathcal{B}_1, \\ & \mathcal{T}_2 := \text{topology on } S_2 \text{ with basis } \mathcal{B}_2) \rightarrow \\ \rightarrow & \mathcal{C} = \{U \times V \mid U \in \mathcal{B}_1, V \in \mathcal{B}_2\} \equiv \text{basis for } \mathcal{T} \end{aligned}$$

319. Theorem

$$\mathcal{X} = \{U \times S_2 \mid U \in \mathcal{B}_1\} \cup \{S_1 \times V \mid V \in \mathcal{B}_2\} \equiv \text{subbasis for } \mathcal{T}$$

320. $\mathcal{T} :=$ product topology on $S_1 \times S_2$

321. [3]

Product Topology, Basis, Cartesian Product (n)

322. Theorem

$$\begin{aligned} & \forall i \in \{1, 2, \dots, n\} : \mathcal{T}_i := \text{topology on } S_i \rightarrow \\ \rightarrow & \mathcal{B} = \{U_1 \times U_2 \times \dots \times U_n \mid U_1 \in \mathcal{T}_1, U_2 \in \mathcal{T}_2, \dots, U_n \in \mathcal{T}_n\} \equiv \text{basis for } \mathcal{T} \end{aligned}$$

323. Theorem

$$\begin{aligned} & \forall i \in \{1, 2, \dots, n\} : \mathcal{B}_i := \text{bases for } \mathcal{T}_i \rightarrow \\ \rightarrow & \mathcal{B} = \{U_1 \times U_2 \times \dots \times U_n \mid U_1 \in \mathcal{B}_1, U_2 \in \mathcal{B}_2, \dots, U_n \in \mathcal{B}_n\} \equiv \text{basis for } \mathcal{T} \end{aligned}$$

324. $\mathcal{T} :=$ product topology on $S_1 \times S_2 \times \dots \times S_n$

325. [3]

General Cartesian product

326. Definition

$$\prod_{k \in K} S_k := \{f : K \rightarrow S \mid \forall k \in K (f(k) \in S_k)\}$$

327. $K :=$ index set

328. $S_k :=$ set for each $k \in K :=$ union of all elements S_k

329. $S := \cup\{S_k \mid k \in K\}$

330. $\{S_k \mid k \in K\} :=$ indexed by k

331. $\prod S_k :=$ general Cartesian product of $\{S_k \mid k \in K\}$

332. [3]

Product Topology on a general Cartesian product, Box Topology

333. Theorem

$$\mathcal{B} = \left\{ \prod U_k \mid \forall k \in K : (U_k \in \mathcal{T}_k) \wedge (U_k = S_k) \right\} \equiv \text{basis for } \mathcal{T}$$

334. Theorem

$$\mathcal{B}' = \left\{ \prod U_k \mid \forall k \in K' : (U_k \in \mathcal{T}_k) \wedge (U_k = S_k) \right\} \equiv \text{basis for } \mathcal{T}'$$

335. $K :=$ *finite* index set

336. $K' :=$ *infinite* index set

337. $(S_k, \mathcal{T}_k) :=$ *topological space* for each $k \in K$

338. $\mathcal{T} :=$ product topology on $\prod S_k$

339. $\mathcal{T}' :=$ box topology

340. \mathcal{T}' is *strictly finer* than \mathcal{T} ,

$$\mathcal{T} \subset \mathcal{T}'.$$

341. [3]

Kolmogorov space (T_0 -space)

342. Definition

$$\forall x, y \in S (x \neq y) \exists U \in \mathcal{T} : (x \in U \wedge y \notin U) \vee (x \notin U \wedge y \in U) \rightarrow \\ \rightarrow (S, \mathcal{T}) \equiv \text{Kolmogorov space } (T_0\text{-space})$$

343. $(S, \mathcal{T}) :=$ topological space

344. [3]

T_1 -space (Fréchet)

345. Definition

$$\forall x, y \in S \ (x \neq y) \ \exists U, V \in \mathcal{T} : (x \in U, y \notin U, x \notin V, y \in V) \\ \rightarrow (S, \mathcal{T}) \equiv T_1\text{-space (Fréchet or accessible space)}$$

346. $(S, \mathcal{T}) :=$ topological space

347. [3]

Cofinite Topology

348. Definition

$\mathcal{T} \equiv$ cofinite topology on S

349. $\mathcal{T} :=$ topology generated by the basis \mathcal{B}

350. $\mathcal{B} = \{X \subseteq S : S \setminus X \text{ is finite}\}$

351. [3]

Cofinite Topology on \mathbb{R}

352. Definition

($\mathcal{T} :=$ topology generated by the basis \mathcal{B} ,
 $\mathcal{B} = \{X \subseteq \mathbb{R} : \mathbb{R} \setminus X \text{ is finite}\}) \rightarrow$
 $\rightarrow \mathcal{T} \equiv$ cofinite topology on \mathbb{R}

353. Theorem: \mathcal{T} is *strictly coarser* than \mathcal{T}_{st} ,

$$\mathcal{T} \subset \mathcal{T}_{st}.$$

354. Theorem

$$(\mathbb{R}, \mathcal{T}) \equiv T_1\text{-space}$$

355. $\mathcal{T}_{st} :=$ standard topology

356. [3]

T_1 -space, Closed

357. Theorem

$$((S, \mathcal{T}) \equiv T_1\text{-space}) \leftrightarrow (\forall x \in S, \{x\} \equiv \text{closed in } (S, \mathcal{T}))$$

358. $(S, \mathcal{T}) :=$ topological space

359. [3]

T_1 -space, Accumulation Point

360. Theorem

$x \equiv$ accumulation point of A
iff
 $\forall \mathcal{O} \subseteq S (x \in \mathcal{O}) \exists_{\infty} a \in \mathcal{O}$

361. $(S, \mathcal{T}) := T_1$ -space

362. $A \subseteq S; \quad a \in A$

363. $\mathcal{O} :=$ open set

364. $\exists_{\infty} :=$ there are infinitely many

365. [3]

Multiple limits (multiple convergence)

366. Theorem: In T_1 -spaces, *sequences may converge to multiple limits.*

367. [3]

Line with two origins

368.

$(S, \mathcal{T}) \equiv$ line with two origins (topological space)

369. Theorems

370.

$(S, \mathcal{T}) \equiv T_1$ -space

371.

$\left(\frac{1}{n+1}\right) \rightarrow \{0, c\}$

372.

\mathcal{B} covers S

373.

\mathcal{B} has the intersection containment property

374. $S := \mathbb{R} \cup \{c\}$

375. $c \notin \mathbb{R}$

376. $\mathcal{B} := \{(a, b) \mid (a, b) \subseteq \mathbb{R}\} \cup \{(-a, 0) \cup \{c\} \cup (0, b)\}$

377. *There are two origins (0 and c).*

378. $\mathcal{B} :=$ basis for a topology \mathcal{T} on S

379. $s = \left(\frac{1}{n+1}\right) :=$ sequence

380. s converges to both 0 and c .

381. $(a, b) :=$ open interval in \mathbb{R}

382. [3]

Cofinite Topology on \mathbb{N}

383. Theorems

384.

$(\mathbb{N}, \mathcal{T}) \equiv$ cofinite topology on \mathbb{N}

385.

$(\mathbb{N}, \mathcal{T}) \equiv T_1$ -space

386.

$\forall m \in \mathbb{N} : (n) \rightarrow m$

387. $\mathcal{T} :=$ topology generated by the basis \mathcal{B}

388. $\mathcal{B} = \{X \subseteq \mathbb{N} : \mathbb{N} \setminus X \text{ is finite}\}$

389. $(n) :=$ sequence

390. (n) converges to every natural number in T_1 -space.

391. [3]

T_2 -space (Hausdorff)

392. Definition

$$\begin{aligned} \forall x, y \in S \ (x \neq y) \ \exists U, V \in \mathcal{T} : (x \in U, y \in V, U \cap V = \emptyset) \\ \rightarrow (S, \mathcal{T}) \equiv T_2\text{-space (Hausdorff)} \end{aligned}$$

393. $(S, \mathcal{T}) :=$ topological space

394. [3]

Unique Limit, Convergence, T_2 -space

395. Theorem

$$((s_n) \equiv \text{convergent}) \rightarrow \left(\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} (s_n) \equiv \text{unique} \right)$$

396. $(S, \mathcal{T}) := T_2\text{-space}$

397. $(s_n) := \text{sequence in } T_2\text{-space}$

398. [3]

T_3 -space (Regular)

399. Definition

$(S, \mathcal{T}) \equiv T_1$ -space, $X \equiv$ closed set,
 $\forall x \in S, X \subseteq S \setminus \{x\}, \exists U, V \in \mathcal{T} : (x \in U, X \subseteq V, U \cap V = \emptyset) \rightarrow$
 $\rightarrow (S, \mathcal{T}) := T_3$ -space (Regular)

400. $(S, \mathcal{T}) :=$ topological space

401. [3]

Clopen set

402. Definition: *Both* open and closed.

403. [3]

T_4 -space (Normal)

404. Definition

$(S, \mathcal{T}) \equiv T_1$ -space, $\forall (X, Y) : X \cap Y = \emptyset, X, Y \equiv \text{closed}, X, Y \subseteq S,$
 $\exists U, V \in \mathcal{T} : (X \subseteq U, Y \subseteq V, U \cap V = \emptyset) \rightarrow$
 $\rightarrow (S, \mathcal{T}) := T_4$ -space (Normal)

405. $(S, \mathcal{T}) :=$ topological space

406. [3]

Separation and Countability Axioms

407. Axioms

408. Separation Axioms \equiv (definitions of) T_0, T_1, T_2, T_3, T_4 .
(they all “separate” points and/or closed sets from each other by open sets)

409. Countability Axioms

(i) Separable Spaces

(ii) First-Countable Spaces

(iii) Second-Countable Spaces

410. [3]

Separable Spaces

411. Definition

$$(\overline{A} = S) \rightarrow (A := \text{dense})$$

412. Definition

$$(\exists A : A \equiv \text{dense, countable}) \rightarrow ((S, \mathcal{T}) := \text{separable})$$

413. $A \subseteq S$

414. $\overline{A} :=$ closure of A in S

415. $(S, \mathcal{T}) :=$ topological space

416. [3]

First-Countable Spaces

417. Definition

$\mathcal{B} :=$ countable basis at x if

(i) $V \in \mathcal{B} \rightarrow x \in V$

(ii) $\forall U : x \in U, \exists V \in \mathcal{B} (V \subseteq U)$

418. $x \in S$

419. $U :=$ open set

420. $(S, \mathcal{T}) :=$ topological space

421. [3]

First-Countable, Closure, Sequence, Convergence

422. Theorem

$$((S, \mathcal{T}) \equiv \text{first-countable}, x \in \overline{A}) \Rightarrow (\exists (s_n) : s_n \rightarrow x)$$

423. $\overline{A} :=$ closure of A in S

424. $(s_n) :=$ sequence

425. $(S, \mathcal{T}) :=$ topological space

426. [3]

Second-Countable Spaces

427. Definition

$$\exists \mathcal{B} \rightarrow (S, \mathcal{T}) := \text{second-countable}$$

428. Theorem

$$\forall \mathcal{T} \equiv \text{second-countable} \rightarrow \mathcal{T} \equiv \text{separable}$$

429. $\mathcal{B} :=$ countable basis of (S, \mathcal{T})

430. $(S, \mathcal{T}) :=$ topological space

431. [3]

Metric (distance function)

432. Definition

$$d : S \times S \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$$

$$(a) \quad \forall x, y \in S : (d(x, y) = 0) \leftrightarrow (x = y)$$

$$(b) \quad \forall x, y \in S : d(x, y) = d(y, x)$$

$$(c) \quad \forall x, y, z \in S : d(x, z) \leq d(x, y) + d(y, z)$$

433. Theorem: $\forall x, y \in S : d(x, y) \geq 0$.

434. [3]

Metric space

435. Definition

$(S, d) :=$ metric space

436. $S :=$ set

437. $d :=$ metric (distance function)

438. $d : S \times S \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$

439. [3]

Open ball

440. Definition

$$B_r(a) := \{x \in S \mid d(a, x) < r\}$$

441. $(S, d) :=$ metric space

442. $a \in S$; $r \in \mathbb{R}^+$

443. $B_r(a) \equiv B_r(a; d) :=$ open ball (center a , radius r)

444. $\mathcal{B} = \{B_r(a) \mid a \in S, r \in \mathbb{R}^+\}$ covers S .

445. [3]

Metrizable Topological Space

446. Definition

(S, \mathcal{T}) is metrizable if
 $\exists d : \mathcal{T}$ is *generated* from the *open balls* in (S, d)

447. $d :=$ metric; $d : S \times S \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$

448. $(S, \mathcal{T}) :=$ topological space

449. d induces \mathcal{T}

450. $\mathcal{T} :=$ metric topology (on S) induced by d

451. ***Different metrics can induce the same topology.***

452. [3]

Euclidean Metric, Unitary Metric

453. Definitions

454.

$$d(x, y) = |x - y| := \text{Euclidean metric}$$

455.

$$k(z, w) = |z - w| := \text{unitary metric}$$

456. $n \in \mathbb{Z}^+ = \{1, 2, 3, \dots\}$

457. $d : \mathbb{R}^n \times \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$

458. $k : \mathbb{C}^n \times \mathbb{C}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$

459. $(\mathbb{R}^n, d), (\mathbb{C}^n, k) := \text{metric spaces}$

460. $|x - y| := \text{Euclidean norm}$

461. $|z - w| := \text{unitary norm}$

462. [3]

Square Metric on \mathbb{R}^n

463. Definition

$$\rho(x, y) := \max\{|x_1 - y_1|, \dots, |x_n - y_n|\} := \text{square metric on } \mathbb{R}^n$$

464. $\rho : \mathbb{R}^n \times \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$

465. $n = 1 \rightarrow \rho :=$ Euclidean metric

466. ρ and d induce the *product topology* on \mathbb{R}^n .

467. [3]

Discrete Metric

468. Definition

$$d(x, y) = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } x = y \\ 1, & \text{if } x \neq y \end{cases}$$

469. $d: S \times S \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$

470. $d :=$ discrete metric on S

471. [3]

Standard Bounded Metric

472. Definition

$$(\exists M \in \mathbb{R}^+ : \forall x, y \in A, d(x, y) \leq M) \equiv (A := \text{bounded in } S)$$

473. Theorem

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{d} : S \times S \rightarrow \mathbb{R}; \quad \bar{d}(x, y) = \min\{1, d(x, y)\} &\Rightarrow \\ &\Rightarrow (S, \bar{d}) \equiv \text{metric space} \end{aligned}$$

474. Theorem

$$\bar{d} \equiv \text{bounded}$$

475. Theorem

$$\bar{d}, d \text{ induce the same topology}$$

476. $(S, d) := \text{metric space}$

477. $A \subseteq S$

478. $\text{diam } A = \sup\{d(x, y) \mid x, y \in A\} := \text{diameter of } A$

479. $\bar{d} := \text{standard bounded metric corresponding to } d$

480. boundedness \neq topological property

481. [3]

Uniform Topology

482. Definition

$$\rho(x, y) := \sup\{\bar{d}(x_k, y_k) \mid k \in K\}$$

483. $d: \mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$; $d(x, y) = |x - y|$; $d \neq$ bounded

484. $(S, d) \equiv$ metric space

485. $K :=$ index set

486. ${}^K S :=$ set of functions from K to S

487. $\rho: {}^K S \times {}^K S \rightarrow S$

488. $({}^K S, \rho) \equiv$ metric space

489. $\bar{d} :=$ standard bounded metric corresponding to d

490. $\rho :=$ uniform metric on ${}^K S$

491. Theorem: ρ induces \mathcal{T}_u .

492. $\mathcal{T}_u :=$ uniform topology on ${}^K S$

493. $\mathcal{T}_p :=$ product topology on ${}^K S$

494. Theorem: \mathcal{T}_u is finer than \mathcal{T}_p ,

$$\mathcal{T}_p \subseteq \mathcal{T}_u.$$

495. [3]

Convergence

496. Definition

$$(\forall U \subseteq S (s \in U) \exists K \in \mathbb{N} : n > K \rightarrow s_n \in U) \Rightarrow (s_n \rightarrow s)$$

497. $(S, \mathcal{T}) :=$ topological space

498. $(s_n) :=$ sequence

499. $\forall n \in \mathbb{N} : s_n \in S$

500. $U :=$ open set

501. $(s_n \rightarrow s) := s_n$ converges to $s \in S$

502. [3]

Metrizable Topological Space, Induced by a Metric, Convergence

503. Theorem

$$\begin{aligned} & s_n \rightarrow s \equiv \\ \equiv & \forall B_r(s) \subseteq S \exists K \in \mathbb{N} : n > K \Rightarrow s_n \in B_r(s) \equiv \\ \equiv & \forall r \in \mathbb{R}^+ \exists K \in \mathbb{N} : n > K \Rightarrow d(s_n, s) < r \end{aligned}$$

504. $(S, \mathcal{T}) :=$ metrizable topological space

505. $\mathcal{T} :=$ induced by the metric d

506. $s \in S$

507. $(s_n) :=$ sequence

508. $\forall n \in \mathbb{N} (s_n \in S)$

509. $B_r(s) :=$ open ball (radius r , center s)

510. $(s_n \rightarrow s) := s_n$ converges to $s \in S$

511. [3]

Cauchy Sequence

512. Definition

$$\forall r \in \mathbb{R}^+ \exists K \in \mathbb{N} : m \geq n > K \Rightarrow d(s_m, s_n) < r$$

513. $(S, \mathcal{T}) :=$ metrizable topological space

514. $\mathcal{T} :=$ induced by the metric d

515. $(s_n) :=$ sequence in S ; $s_n \rightarrow s$

516. $(s_n) :=$ Cauchy sequence

517. $\neg \square :=$ not necessarily

518. Theorem: $\forall (s'_n) \equiv$ Cauchy sequence : $\neg \square (s'_n) \equiv$ converges.

519. [3]

Cauchy Sequence Bounded by a Rational Number

520. Theorem

$\forall (x_n) : (x_n) \equiv \text{Cauchy sequence of rational numbers} \rightarrow$
 $\rightarrow (x_n) \equiv \text{bounded by } q \in \mathbb{Q}$

521. $(x_n) := \text{Cauchy sequence of rational numbers}$

522. [3]

Complete Metric Space

523. Definition

$(\forall (s_n) : s_n \rightarrow s \in S) \Rightarrow (S, d) := \text{complete metric space}$

524. $(S, d) := \text{metric space}$

525. $(s_n) := \text{Cauchy sequence}$

526. [3]

Subsequence

527. Definition

$(f \circ g : \mathbb{N} \rightarrow S) :=$ subsequence of f

528. $(s_n) :=$ sequence in S

529. $(s_n) \equiv (f : \mathbb{N} \rightarrow S, \forall n \in \mathbb{N} : f(n) = s_n)$

530. $g : \mathbb{N} \rightarrow \mathbb{N}$

531. $g :=$ strictly increasing function

532. [3]

Cauchy Sequence, Subsequence, Convergence

533. Theorem

$$(\exists s \in S : s_{n_k} \rightarrow s) \Rightarrow (s_n \rightarrow s)$$

534. $(S, d) :=$ metric space

535. $(s_n) :=$ Cauchy sequence in S

536. $(s_{n_k}) :=$ subsequence of (s_n)

537. [3]

Complete Metric Space, Cauchy Sequence, Subsequence, Convergence

538. Theorem

$$((S, d) \equiv \text{complete}) \Leftrightarrow (\forall (s_n) \text{ in } S, \exists (s_{n_k}) : s_{n_k} \rightarrow s \in S)$$

539. $(S, d) :=$ metric space

540. $(s_n) :=$ Cauchy sequence in S

541. $(s_{n_k}) :=$ subsequence of (s_n)

542. [3]

Bounded Sequence

543. Theorem

$$\begin{aligned} \{s_n\} \equiv \text{bounded} &\rightarrow (s_n) \equiv \text{bounded} \\ &\equiv \\ (\exists M \in \mathbb{R}^+ : \forall n, m \in \mathbb{N}, d(s_n, s_m) \leq M) &\rightarrow ((s_n) \equiv \text{bounded in } S) \end{aligned}$$

544. $(S, d) :=$ metric space

545. $(s_n) :=$ sequence in S

546. [3]

Metric Space, Cauchy Sequence, Bounded

547. Theorem

$$\begin{aligned}(S, d) \equiv \text{metric space, } (s_n) \equiv \text{Cauchy sequence in } S &\Rightarrow \\ &\Rightarrow (s_n) \equiv \text{bounded in } S\end{aligned}$$

548. [3]

Bolzano-Weierstrass Property

549. Definition

$$\begin{aligned} & (\forall (s_n) \exists (s_{n_k}) s_{n_k} \rightarrow s \in S) \Rightarrow \\ \Rightarrow & (S, d) \text{ has the Bolzano-Weierstrass Property} \end{aligned}$$

550. $(S, d) :=$ metric space

551. $(s_n) :=$ sequence *bounded* in S

552. $(s_{n_k}) :=$ subsequence of (s_n)

553. [3]

Euclidean Space, Unitary Space, Complete Metric Spaces $\mathbb{R}^n, \mathbb{C}^n$

554. Theorem

$\forall n \in \mathbb{N} : (\mathbb{R}^n, d), (\mathbb{C}^n, k) \equiv \text{complete metric spaces}$

555. $d :=$ Euclidean metric

556. $k :=$ unitary metric

557. [3]

Standard Bounded Metric on \mathbb{R} , Supremum, Complete Metric Space, Metric Induces the Product Topology on the Index Set

558. Theorem

$$\begin{aligned} S = {}^{\mathbb{N}}\mathbb{R}, \quad (\bar{d} : \mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}) &\equiv \text{standard bounded metric on } \mathbb{R}, \\ d^* : {}^{\mathbb{N}}\mathbb{R} \times {}^{\mathbb{N}}\mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}, \quad d^*(x, y) &= \sup \left\{ \frac{\bar{d}(x_k, y_k)}{k+1} \mid k \in \mathbb{N} \right\} \Rightarrow \\ &\Rightarrow (S, d^* \equiv \text{complete metric space, } d^* \text{ induces } \mathcal{T}_p) \end{aligned}$$

559. $\mathcal{T}_p :=$ product topology on $S = {}^{\mathbb{N}}\mathbb{R}$

560. [3]

Covering

561. Definition

$$(\bigcup \mathcal{C} = S) \rightarrow (\mathcal{C} := \text{covering of } S)$$
$$\mathcal{C} \text{ covers } S$$

562. Definition

$$(\mathcal{C} := \text{covering of } S) \wedge (\forall U \in \mathcal{C} : U \equiv \text{open set}) \rightarrow$$
$$\rightarrow \mathcal{C} := \text{open covering of } S$$

563. $(S, \mathcal{T}) :=$ topological space

564. $\mathcal{C} :=$ collection of subsets of S

565. $\bigcup \mathcal{C} :=$ union of all elements of \mathcal{C}

566. [3]

Compact, Subcover

567. Definition

$(\forall \mathcal{C} : \exists_n \text{ subcover of the covering}) \rightarrow (S, \mathcal{T}) := \text{compact}$

568. $(S, \mathcal{T}) := \text{topological space}$

569. $\mathcal{C} := \text{collection of subsets of } S$

570. $\mathcal{C} := \text{open covering of } S$

571. $\exists_n := \text{there is a finite number of}$

572. $\text{subcover of the covering} := \text{subcollection that covers } S$

573. [3]

Finite Intersection Property, Subcollection

574. Definition

$(\forall \mathcal{D} \subseteq \mathcal{C} : \bigcap \mathcal{D} \neq \emptyset) \rightarrow (\mathcal{C} \text{ has the finite intersection property})$

575. $(S, \mathcal{T}) :=$ topological space

576. $\mathcal{C} :=$ collection of subsets of S

577. $\mathcal{D} :=$ finite subcollection

578. $\bigcap \mathcal{C} :=$ intersection of all elements of \mathcal{C}

579. [3]

Compact, Closed, Finite Intersection Property

580. Theorem

$$((S, \mathcal{T}) \equiv \text{compact}) \leftrightarrow (\forall \mathcal{C} : \bigcap \mathcal{C} \neq \emptyset)$$

581. $(S, \mathcal{T}) :=$ topological space

582. $\mathcal{C} :=$ collection of *closed sets* in S with the *finite intersection property*

583. $\bigcap \mathcal{C} :=$ intersection of all elements of \mathcal{C}

584. [3]

Nested sequence

585. Definition

$$B_0 \supseteq B_1 \supseteq B_2 \supseteq \dots$$

586. $(S, \mathcal{T}) :=$ compact topological space

587. $B_i :=$ nonempty *closed sets* in S

588. Theorem: $\mathcal{C} = \{B_k \mid k \in \mathbb{N}, j < k \rightarrow B_k \subseteq B_j\}$ has the *finite intersection property*.

589. $\mathcal{C} :=$ nested sequence of nonempty *closed sets* in S

590. [3]

Compact, Finite Subcollection, Cover, Finite Intersection Property, Covering, Basis, Basic Open Sets, Basic Closed Sets

591. Theorem

$$\begin{aligned} & (S, \mathcal{T}) \text{ is compact} \equiv \\ & \equiv \forall \mathcal{C}_S : \mathcal{C}_S \text{ contains a finite subcollection that covers } S \equiv \\ & \equiv (\forall \mathcal{C}' : \mathcal{C}' \text{ has the finite intersection property}) \rightarrow \bigcup \mathcal{C}' \neq \emptyset \end{aligned}$$

592. $(S, \mathcal{T}) :=$ topological space

593. $\mathcal{C}_S :=$ covering of S by B_i

594. $\mathcal{B} :=$ basis for the topology \mathcal{T}

595. $B_i \in \mathcal{B}$

596. $B_i :=$ basic open sets in S

597. $B'_i = S \setminus B_i :=$ basic closed sets in S

598. $\mathcal{C}' = \{B'_i\}$

599. $\bigcup \mathcal{C}' :=$ union of all elements of \mathcal{C}'

600. [3]

Tychonoff's Theorem

601. Theorem

$$\begin{aligned} (\forall k \in K : (S_k, \mathcal{T}_k) \equiv \text{compact topological space}) &\rightarrow \\ &\rightarrow \left(\prod_{k \in K} S_k \equiv \text{compact in } \mathcal{T}_p \right) \end{aligned}$$

602.

$$\prod_{k \in K} S_k = \{f : K \rightarrow S \mid \forall k \in K (f(k) \in S_k)\}$$

603. $K :=$ index set

604. $S_k :=$ set for each $k \in K$

605. $\{S_k \mid k \in K\} :=$ indexed by k

606. $S = \cup\{S_k \mid k \in K\}$

607. $\prod S_k :=$ general Cartesian product of $\{S_k \mid k \in K\}$

608. $\mathcal{T}_p :=$ product topology

609. [3]

Heine-Borel Theorem

610. Theorem

$$((A, \mathcal{T}_A) \equiv \text{compact}) \leftrightarrow (A \equiv \text{closed and bounded in } \mathbb{R})$$

611. $A \subseteq \mathbb{R}$

612. $(A, \mathcal{T}_A) :=$ topological space

613. [3]

Bounded, Supremum, Infimum, Closure

614. Theorem

$$(A \equiv \text{bounded}) \rightarrow (\sup A, \inf A \in \overline{A})$$

615. $A \neq \emptyset$; $A \subseteq \mathbb{R}$

616. $\overline{A} :=$ closure of A in \mathbb{R}

617. [3]

Covering by Sets, Open Covering by Open Sets, Subspace

618. Definition

$\mathcal{C} :=$ covering of A by sets in S

619. Definition

$(\forall C \in \mathcal{C} : C \text{ open in } S) \rightarrow$
 $\rightarrow (\mathcal{C} := \text{open covering of } A \text{ by open sets in } S)$

620. $(S, \mathcal{T}) :=$ topological space

621. $(A, \mathcal{T}_A) :=$ subspace of (S, \mathcal{T})

622. $\mathcal{C} = \{S_i \mid S_i \in S, A \subseteq \cup \mathcal{C}\}$

623. [3]

Compact, Subspace, Open Covering, Subcollection

624. Theorem

$$((A, \mathcal{T}_A) \equiv \text{compact}) \leftrightarrow (\forall \mathcal{C} : \mathcal{C}' \in \mathcal{C})$$

625. $(S, \mathcal{T}) :=$ topological space

626. $(A, \mathcal{T}_A) :=$ subspace of (S, \mathcal{T})

627. $\mathcal{C} :=$ open covering of A by open sets in S

628. $\mathcal{C}' :=$ finite subcollection that covers A

629. [3]

T_2 -space, Subspace, Compact, Closed

630. Theorem

$$((A, \mathcal{T}_A) \equiv \text{compact}) \rightarrow (A \equiv \text{closed in } S)$$

631. $(S, \mathcal{T}) := T_2$ space

632. $(A, \mathcal{T}_A) :=$ subspace of (S, \mathcal{T})

633. [3]

Closed, Compact, Subspace

634. Theorem

$$(A \equiv \text{closed in } S) \rightarrow (A, \mathcal{T}_A) \equiv \text{compact}$$

635. $(S, \mathcal{T}) :=$ compact topological space

636. $(A, \mathcal{T}_A) :=$ subspace of (S, \mathcal{T})

637. [3]

Generalized Heine-Borel Theorem

638. Theorem

$$((A, \mathcal{T}_A) \equiv \text{compact}) \leftrightarrow (A \equiv \text{closed and bounded in } \mathbb{R}^n)$$

639. $A \subseteq \mathbb{R}$

640. $(A, \mathcal{T}_A) := \text{topological space}$

641. [3]

Sequentially Compact

642. Definition

$\forall n((s_n) \in S, \exists(s'_n) : s'_n \rightarrow s) \rightarrow (S, d) \equiv \text{sequentially compact}$

643. $(S, d) :=$ metric space

644. $(s_n) :=$ sequence in S

645. $(s'_n) :=$ subsequence of (s_n)

646. [3]

Lebesgue number

647. Definition

$(\forall A \subseteq S, \text{diam } A < \delta, \exists C \in \mathcal{C} : A \subseteq C) \rightarrow (\delta := \text{Lebesgue number for } \mathcal{C})$

648. $(S, \mathcal{T}) :=$ topological space

649. $\mathcal{C} :=$ open covering of S

650. $\delta \in \mathbb{R}^+$

651. $\text{diam } A :=$ diameter of A

652. [3]

Lebesgue's Covering Lemma

653. Theorem

$(S, \mathcal{T}) \equiv$ metrizable, sequentially compact \rightarrow
 $\rightarrow \mathcal{C}$ has a Lebesgue number

654. $(S, \mathcal{T}) :=$ topological space

655. $\mathcal{C} :=$ open covering of S

656. [3]

Totally bounded, r -net

657. Definition

$$(S = \bigcup\{B_r(x) \mid x \in A\}) \rightarrow (A \text{ has an } r\text{-net})$$

658. Definition

$$(\forall r \in \mathbb{R}^+ : (S, d) \text{ has an } r\text{-net}) \rightarrow (S, d) \equiv \text{totally bounded}$$

659. $(S, d) :=$ metric space

660. $r \in \mathbb{R}^+$

661. $A \in S$; $A :=$ finite

662. [3]

Sequentially Compact Metric Space, Totally Bounded

663. Theorem

$(S, d) \equiv \text{sequentially compact} \rightarrow (S, d) \equiv \text{totally bounded}$

664. $(S, d) := \text{metric space}$

665. [3]

Metrizable Space, Compact, Accumulation Point, Sequentially Compact, Infinite Subset

666. Theorem

$$\begin{aligned} & (S, \mathcal{T}) \text{ is compact} \equiv \\ \equiv & \forall S' : S' \text{ has an accumulation point} \equiv \\ \equiv & (S, \mathcal{T}) \text{ is sequentially compact} \end{aligned}$$

667. $(S, \mathcal{T}) :=$ metrizable space

668. $S' :=$ *infinite* subset of S

669. [3]

Locally Compact

670. Definition

$$\forall x \in S \exists (K, \mathcal{T}_K) : N(x) \subseteq K \rightarrow (S, \mathcal{T}) := \text{locally compact}$$

671. $(S, \mathcal{T}) :=$ topological space

672. $(K, \mathcal{T}_K) :=$ compact subspace

673. $N(x) :=$ neighborhood of x

674. [3]

One-Point Compactification

675. Definition

$(\bar{S}, \bar{\mathcal{T}}) :=$ one-point compactification of S

676. $(S, \mathcal{T}) :=$ locally compact T_2 space

677. $\bar{S} = S \cup \{\infty\}$

678. $\infty :=$ point at infinity

679. $\bar{\mathcal{T}} = \mathcal{T} \cup \{S \setminus K \mid (K, \mathcal{T}_K)\} :=$ compact subspace of (S, \mathcal{T})

680. [3]

Locally Compact, T_2 -space, One-Point Compactification

681. Theorem

$$\begin{aligned}(S, \mathcal{T}) \equiv \text{locally compact } T_2\text{-space} &\rightarrow \\ &\rightarrow (\bar{S}, \bar{\mathcal{T}}) \equiv \text{compact } T_2\text{-space}\end{aligned}$$

682. $(\bar{S}, \bar{\mathcal{T}}) :=$ one-point compactification of (S, \mathcal{T})

683. [3]

Interior of a Set, Empty Interior, Nowhere Dense, Closure

684. Definition

$$A^\circ := \bigcup_i U_i := \text{interior of } A$$

685. Definition

$$(A = \emptyset) \rightarrow (A \text{ has empty interior})$$

686. Definition

$$(\overline{A})^\circ = \emptyset \rightarrow A := \text{nowhere dense in } S$$

687. $(S, \mathcal{T}) := \text{topological space}$

688. $A \subseteq S$

689. $U_i \subseteq A$

690. $U_i := \text{open set}$

691. $\overline{A} := \text{closure of } A$

692. [3]

Nowhere Dense, Dense, Interior

693. Theorem

$$(A \equiv \text{nowhere dense in } S) \leftrightarrow (S \setminus A)^\circ \equiv \text{dense in } S$$

694. $(S, \mathcal{T}) :=$ topological space

695. $A \subseteq S$

696. $(S \setminus A)^\circ :=$ interior of $(S \setminus A)$

697. [3]

Meagre, Nonmeagre, Comeagre, Countable Union, Nowhere Dense, First Category, Second Category

698. Definition

$$A = \bigcup_c A' \rightarrow$$

$\rightarrow A := \text{meagre (or a set of first category)}$

699. Definition

$$(A \neq \text{meagre}) \rightarrow A := \text{nonmeagre (or a set of second category)}$$

700. Definition

$$(A \equiv \text{meagre}) \rightarrow S \setminus A := \text{comeagre}$$

701. $(S, \mathcal{T}) := \text{topological space}$

702. $A \subseteq S$

703. $\bigcup_c := \text{countable union}$

704. $A' := \text{nowhere dense sets}$

705. [3]

Baire Category Theorem

706. Theorem

(i) $(\forall A : A \equiv \text{comeagre}, A \subseteq S) \rightarrow A \equiv \text{dense in } S$

(ii) $S \equiv \text{nonmeagre}$

707. $(S, \mathcal{T}) := (\text{locally compact } T_2\text{-space}) \vee (\text{completely metrizable space})$

708. [3]

Image, Inverse Image

709. Definitions

710. $f : X \rightarrow Y; \quad A \subseteq X; \quad B \subseteq Y$

711. $f[A] = \{f(x) \mid x \in A\} :=$ image of A under f

712. $f^{-1}[B] = \{x \in X \mid f(x) \in B\} :=$ inverse image of B under f

713. [3]

Continuous Functions

714. Definition

$$(\forall V \in \mathcal{U} : f^{-1}[V] \in \mathcal{T}) \rightarrow (f := \text{continuous})$$

715. Theorem

$$(\forall A : f^{-1}[A] := \text{open}) \rightarrow (f \equiv \text{continuous})$$

716. $(X, \mathcal{T}), (Y, \mathcal{U}) :=$ topological spaces

717. $f : X \rightarrow Y$

718. $A :=$ open set

719. *Continuity may depend on both, the function and the topologies.*

720. Theorem

$$\begin{aligned} (\forall V \in \mathcal{U}, f(x) \in V, \exists U \in \mathcal{T}, x \in U : f[U] \subseteq V) \rightarrow \\ \rightarrow (f \equiv \text{continuous at } x \in X) \end{aligned}$$

721. [3]

Continuous Function

722. Theorem

$$(f \equiv \text{continuous}) \leftrightarrow (\forall x \in A : f \equiv \text{continuous})$$

723. $(A, \mathcal{T}), (B, \mathcal{U}) :=$ topological spaces

724. $f : A \rightarrow B$

725. [3]

Continuity in Metrizable Spaces

726. Theorem

$$(f \equiv \text{continuous at } x \in A) \leftrightarrow \\ \leftrightarrow (\forall \epsilon > 0 \exists \delta > 0 : d(x, y) < \delta \rightarrow \rho(f(x), f(y)) < \epsilon)$$

727. $(A, \mathcal{T}), (B, \mathcal{U}) :=$ metrizable topological spaces

728. $d, \rho :=$ metrics

729. $\mathcal{T}, \mathcal{U} :=$ induced by d and ρ , respectively

730. $f : A \rightarrow B$

731. [3]

Continuous Function, Metrizable Spaces, Open Ball, Sequence, Convergence

732. Theorem

$$\begin{aligned} & f \text{ is continuous at } x \equiv \\ & \equiv \forall B_\epsilon(f(x); \rho) \exists B_\delta(x; d) : f[B_\delta(x; d)] \subseteq B_\epsilon(f(x); \rho) \equiv \\ & \equiv (x_n \rightarrow x) \Rightarrow (f(x_n) \rightarrow f(x)) \end{aligned}$$

733. $(A, \mathcal{T}), (B, \mathcal{U}) :=$ metrizable topological spaces

734. $d, \rho :=$ metrics

735. $\mathcal{T}, \mathcal{U} :=$ induced by d and ρ , respectively

736. $f : A \rightarrow B$

737. $x \in A$

738. $B_\epsilon(f(x); \rho) :=$ open ball in \mathcal{U} (center $f(x)$, radius $\epsilon > 0$, metric ρ)

739. $B_\delta(x; d) :=$ open ball in \mathcal{T} (center x , radius $\delta > 0$, metric d)

740. $(x_n) :=$ sequence

741. $(x_n \rightarrow x) := x_n$ converges to x

742. [3]

Uniformly Continuous Function

743. Definition

$$\forall \epsilon > 0 \exists \delta > 0 \forall a, b \in A (d(a, b) < \delta \rightarrow \rho(f(a), f(b)) < \epsilon) \rightarrow \\ \rightarrow f := \text{uniformly continuous on } A$$

744. $(A, \mathcal{T}), (B, \mathcal{U}) :=$ metrizable topological spaces

745. $d, \rho :=$ metrics

746. $\mathcal{T}, \mathcal{U} :=$ induced by d and ρ , respectively

747. $f : A \rightarrow B$

748. [3]

Homeomorphism

749. Definition

$(f \equiv \text{bijection} : O \in \mathcal{T} \leftrightarrow f[O] \in \mathcal{U}) \rightarrow (f := \text{homeomorphism})$

750. $(A, \mathcal{T}), (B, \mathcal{U}) := \text{topological spaces}$

751. $f : A \rightarrow B$

752. [3]

Homeomorphic (Topologically Equivalent) Spaces

753. Definition

$$\exists f_h \rightarrow (A, \mathcal{T}) \equiv_t (B, \mathcal{U})$$

754. $(A, \mathcal{T}), (B, \mathcal{U}) :=$ topological spaces

755. $(f_h : A \rightarrow B) :=$ homeomorphism

756. $\equiv_t :=$ topological equivalence

757. [3]

Topological Property (Topological Invariant)

758. Definition

topological invariant := *property preserved under homeomorphisms*

$$(\mathcal{T} \text{ has } P) \wedge (\mathcal{U} \equiv_t \mathcal{T}) \rightarrow (\mathcal{U} \text{ has } P)$$

759. $P :=$ topological property

760. $(A, \mathcal{T}), (B, \mathcal{U}) :=$ topological spaces

761. $\equiv_t :=$ topological equivalence

762. Examples of *topological invariants*: compactness, being a T_2 -space, separation axioms (T_0 - T_4), countability axioms, metrizability.

763. [3]

T_2 -space, Topological Invariance

764. Theorem

$$((A, \mathcal{T}) := T_2\text{-space}) \wedge ((B, \mathcal{U}) \equiv_t (A, \mathcal{T})) \rightarrow (B, \mathcal{U}) \equiv T_2\text{-space}$$

765. $(A, \mathcal{T}), (B, \mathcal{U}) :=$ topological spaces

766. $\equiv_t :=$ topological equivalence

767. [3]

Tychonoff Space

768. Definition

$$\begin{aligned} & (\mathcal{T} \equiv T_1\text{-space}) \wedge \\ & \wedge (\forall x \in S, \forall A \subseteq S \setminus \{x\}, \exists f : S \rightarrow [0, 1], f(x) = 0, f[A] = \{1\}) \rightarrow \\ & \rightarrow \mathcal{T} := \text{Tychonoff space} \end{aligned}$$

769. $(S, \mathcal{T}) :=$ topological space

770. $A :=$ closed set

771. $f :=$ continuous function

772. [3]

Completely Regular Space ($T_{3\frac{1}{2}}$ -space)

773. Definition

$(\forall x \in S, \forall A \subseteq S \setminus \{x\}, \exists f : S \rightarrow [0, 1], f(x) = 0, f[A] = \{1\}) \rightarrow$
 $\rightarrow \mathcal{T} := \text{completely regular space } (T_{3\frac{1}{2}}\text{-space})$

774. $(S, \mathcal{T}) := \text{topological space}$

775. $A := \text{closed set}$

776. $f := \text{continuous function}$

777. [3]

Urysohn's Lemma

778. Theorem

$$\begin{aligned} & ((S, \mathcal{T}) \equiv T_4\text{-space}) \wedge (A \cap B = \emptyset) \rightarrow \\ & \rightarrow \exists f : S \rightarrow [0, 1], f[A] = \{0\}, f[B] = \{1\} \end{aligned}$$

779. $A, B :=$ closed subsets of S

780. $f :=$ continuous function

781. [3]

T_4 -space, Tychonoff Space

782. Theorem

$$(\forall \mathcal{T} : \mathcal{T} \equiv T_4\text{-space}) \rightarrow (\mathcal{T} \equiv \text{Tychonoff space})$$

783. $\mathcal{T} :=$ topological space

784. [3]

Tietze Extension Theorem

785. Theorem

$(S, \mathcal{T}) \equiv T_4$ -space,

$(C, \mathcal{T}_C) \subseteq_s (S, \mathcal{T})$,

$C \equiv$ closed in S ,

$a, b \in \mathbb{R} : a < b$,

$f : C \rightarrow [a, b]$ continuous

\implies

f can be extended to $g : S \rightarrow [a, b]$ continuous

786. \subseteq_s := subspace relation

787. [3]

Disconnection, Disconnected, Connected

788. Definitions

789.

$(U, V) :=$ disconnection of S

790.

$\exists(U, V) \rightarrow (S, \mathcal{T}) :=$ disconnected

791.

$\nexists(U, V) \rightarrow (S, \mathcal{T}) :=$ connected

792. $(S, \mathcal{T}) :=$ topological space

793. $U, V :=$ nonempty open sets

794. $U \cap V = \emptyset$

795. $U \cup V = S$

796. [3]

Connected, Clopen, Uniqueness

797. Theorem

$$(S, \mathcal{T}) \equiv \text{connected} \leftrightarrow \exists! \mathcal{C} : \mathcal{C} = \{S, \emptyset\}$$

798. $(S, \mathcal{T}) :=$ topological space

799. $\mathcal{C} :=$ set of clopen sets in S

800. $\exists! :=$ there is *exactly* one

801. [3]

Interval, Connected Subspace, Standard Topology

802. Theorem

$$I \subseteq \mathbb{R} \rightarrow (I, \mathcal{T}_I) \equiv \text{connected subspace of } (\mathbb{R}, \mathcal{T})$$

803. $I :=$ interval

804. $\mathcal{T} :=$ standard topology on \mathbb{R}

805. [3]

Connected Subspace, Standard Topology, Interval

806. Theorem

$$A \subseteq \mathbb{R}, \quad (A, \mathcal{T}_A) \equiv \text{connected subspace of } (\mathbb{R}, \mathcal{T}) \rightarrow \\ \rightarrow A \equiv \text{interval}$$

807. $\mathcal{T} :=$ standard topology on \mathbb{R}

808. [3]

Connected, Continuous, Image

809. Theorem

$(A, \mathcal{T}) \equiv \text{connected}, f : A \rightarrow B \text{ continuous} \rightarrow$
 $f[A] \equiv \text{connected}$

810. $(A, \mathcal{T}), (B, \mathcal{U}) := \text{topological spaces}$

811. [3]

Intermediate Value Theorem

812. Theorem

$(S, \mathcal{T}) \equiv \text{connected}, \quad f : S \rightarrow \mathbb{R} \text{ continuous} \rightarrow$
 $\rightarrow f[S] \equiv \text{interval}$

813. $(S, \mathcal{T}) := \text{topological space}$

814. [3]

Topology Generated by a Set, Connected Subspace

815. Theorem

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{A} &= \{(A_k, \mathcal{T}_{A_k}) \mid k \in K\}, \\ \bigcap \{A_k \mid k \in K\} &\neq \emptyset, \\ A &= \bigcup \{A_k \mid k \in K\}, \\ \mathcal{T}^* &\text{ is generated by } \bigcup \{\mathcal{T}_{A_k} \mid k \in K\} \\ &\implies \\ (A, \mathcal{T}^*) &\equiv \text{connected subspace of } (S, \mathcal{T}) \end{aligned}$$

816. $(S, \mathcal{T}) :=$ topological space

817. $(A_k, \mathcal{T}_{A_k}) :=$ connected subspace of (S, \mathcal{T})

818. $\mathcal{T}^* :=$ topology

819. [3]

Components

820. Definitions

821.

$$x \sim y \iff \exists(A, \mathcal{T}_A) : x, y \in A$$

822.

connected components of $S :=$ *equivalence classes* of \sim

823. $(S, \mathcal{T}) :=$ topological space

824. $\sim :=$ equivalence relation on S

825. $(A, \mathcal{T}_A) :=$ connected subspace of (S, \mathcal{T})

826. [3]

Connected Subspace, Clopen, Closed, Component

827. Theorem

(i) $\forall x \in S \exists! \mathcal{M} : x \in \mathcal{M}$

(ii) $(A, \mathcal{T}_A) \equiv \text{connected subspace of } (S, \mathcal{T}) \rightarrow A \subseteq \mathcal{M}$

(iii) $(A, \mathcal{T}_A) \equiv \text{connected subspace of } (S, \mathcal{T}), A \equiv \text{clopen in } S \rightarrow A \subseteq \mathcal{M}$

(iv) $\forall \mathcal{M} : \mathcal{M} \equiv \text{closed in } S$

828. $(S, \mathcal{T}) := \text{topological space}$

829. $\mathcal{M} := \text{component of } S$

830. [3]

Totally Disconnected

831. Definition

$$\begin{aligned} \forall x, y \in S, x \neq y, \exists(U, V) : x \in U, y \in V \rightarrow \\ \rightarrow (S, \mathcal{T}) := \text{totally disconnected} \end{aligned}$$

832. $(S, \mathcal{T}) :=$ topological space

833. $(U, V) :=$ disconnection of S

834. [3]

Locally Connected Space

835. Definition

$$\begin{aligned} & \forall x \in S, \forall U : x \in U \rightarrow \\ & \rightarrow \exists V, x \in V : (V, \mathcal{T}_V) := \text{connected}, V \subseteq U \end{aligned}$$

836. $(S, \mathcal{T}) :=$ topological space

837. $U, V :=$ open sets in S

838. $\neg \square :=$ not necessarily

839. connected space $\equiv \neg \square$ locally connected

840. [3]

Function Space

841. Definition

function space := vector space + functions (elements)

842. [3]

Example, Function Space, $\mathbb{R}\mathbb{R}$

843. Theorems

844.

$$\mathbb{R}\mathbb{R} = \{f \mid f : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}\}$$

845.

$$\mathbb{R}\mathbb{R} \equiv \text{vector space over } \mathbb{R}$$

846.

$$\mathbb{R}\mathbb{R} \equiv \text{function space}$$

847. $f, g \in \mathbb{R}\mathbb{R} \rightarrow f + g \in \mathbb{R}\mathbb{R}, (f + g)(x) = f(x) + g(x)$

848. $f \in \mathbb{R}\mathbb{R}, c \in \mathbb{R} \rightarrow cf \in \mathbb{R}\mathbb{R}, (cf)(x) = c \cdot f(x)$

849. $\forall x \in \mathbb{R} : 0(x) = 0$

850. $\forall x \in \mathbb{R} : (-f)(x) = -f(x)$

851. $0 :=$ zero vector (function)

852. $-f :=$ additive inverse of $f \in \mathbb{R}\mathbb{R}$

853. [3]

Normed Vector Space

854. Definitions

855.

$(V, | \cdot |)$:= normed vector space (normed linear space)

856. $(| \cdot | : V \rightarrow \mathbb{R})$:= norm (function)

(i) $\forall v \in V, |v| = 0 \leftrightarrow v = 0$

(ii) $\forall v, w \in V, |v + w| \leq |v| + |w|$

(iii) $\forall v \in V, c \in \mathbb{F}, |cv| = |c||v|$

857. V := vector space over a *field* \mathbb{F}

858. $v \in V \rightarrow |v|$:= norm of v

859. $c \in \mathbb{F} \rightarrow |c|$:= absolute value of v

860. [3]

Banach Space

861. Definition

$(V, d) \equiv$ complete metric space $\rightarrow V :=$ Banach space

862. $V :=$ normed vector space induced by d

863. $d :=$ metric

864. [3]

Metric Space, Continuous Function

865. Theorem

$$(S, d) \equiv \text{metric space} \rightarrow \mathcal{C}(S, \mathbb{R}) \leq \mathcal{B}(S, \mathbb{R})$$

$$866. \mathcal{B}(S, \mathbb{R}) = \{f : S \rightarrow \mathbb{R} \mid f := \text{bounded}\}$$

$$867. \mathcal{C}(S, \mathbb{R}) = \{f \in \mathcal{B}(S, \mathbb{R}) \mid f := \text{continuous}\}$$

868. \leq := subspace relation

869. [3]

Closed Subspace of a Banach space

870. Theorem

closed subspace of a Banach space \equiv Banach space

871. $V :=$ Banach space induced by d

872. $d :=$ metric

873. $W :=$ subspace of V (closed in V)

874. [3]

Pointwise Convergence

875. Definition

$$\forall x \in S : f_n(x) \rightarrow f(x) \Rightarrow (f_n) := \text{converges pointwise to } f$$

876. Definition

$$\begin{aligned} (x \in S, \epsilon > 0, \exists K \in \mathbb{N} : n > K \rightarrow |f_n(x) - f(x)| < \epsilon) \Rightarrow \\ \Rightarrow (f_n) := \text{converges pointwise to } f \end{aligned}$$

877. $(f_n) :=$ sequence in $\mathcal{C}(S, \mathbb{R})$

878. $\mathcal{B}(S, \mathbb{R}) = \{f : S \rightarrow \mathbb{R} \mid f := \text{bounded}\}$

879. $\mathcal{C}(S, \mathbb{R}) = \{f \in \mathcal{B}(S, \mathbb{R}) \mid f := \text{continuous}\}$

880. [3]

Uniform Convergence

881. Definition

$$(\epsilon > 0, \exists K \in \mathbb{N} : n > K \rightarrow \forall x \in S, |f_n(x) - f(x)| < \epsilon) \rightarrow \\ \rightarrow (f_n) := \text{converges uniformly to } f$$

882. $(f_n) :=$ sequence in $\mathcal{C}(S, \mathbb{R})$

883. $\mathcal{B}(S, \mathbb{R}) = \{f : S \rightarrow \mathbb{R} \mid f := \text{bounded}\}$

884. $\mathcal{C}(S, \mathbb{R}) = \{f \in \mathcal{B}(S, \mathbb{R}) \mid f := \text{continuous}\}$

885. [3]

Uniform Convergence, Metric Space

886. Theorem

$$(f_n) \equiv \text{converges uniformly to } f \Rightarrow f \in \mathcal{C}(S, \mathbb{R})$$

887. $(S, d) :=$ metric space

888. $(f_n) :=$ sequence in $\mathcal{C}(S, \mathbb{R})$

889. $\mathcal{B}(S, \mathbb{R}) = \{f : S \rightarrow \mathbb{R} \mid f := \text{bounded}\}$

890. $\mathcal{C}(S, \mathbb{R}) = \{f \in \mathcal{B}(S, \mathbb{R}) \mid f := \text{continuous}\}$

891. [3]

Equicontinuous

892. Definition

$$(\epsilon > 0 \rightarrow (\delta > 0 : \forall x, y \in K, \forall f \in \mathcal{A}, d(x, y) < \delta \rightarrow |f(x) - f(y)| < \epsilon)) \Rightarrow \\ \Rightarrow \mathcal{A} := \text{equicontinuous}$$

893. [3]

Arzela-Ascoli Theorem

894. Theorem

$$\mathcal{A} \equiv \text{compact} \leftrightarrow \mathcal{A} \equiv (\text{bounded} \wedge \text{equicontinuous})$$

895. $(K, d) :=$ compact metric space

896. $\mathcal{A} \subseteq \mathcal{C}(K, \mathbb{R})$

897. $\mathcal{A} :=$ closed in K

898. [3]

Homotopy

899. Definitions

900.

$$\begin{aligned} & F : X \times [0, 1] \rightarrow Y \text{ continuous,} \\ \forall x \in X : & F(x, 0) = f(x), F(x, 1) = g(x) := \\ & := \text{homotopy from } f \text{ to } g \end{aligned}$$

901.

F deforms f into g

902.

\exists homotopy from f to $g \rightarrow f \simeq g$

903. $(X, \mathcal{T}), (Y, \mathcal{U}) :=$ topological spaces

904. $(f, x : X \rightarrow Y) :=$ continuous

905. $\simeq :=$ homotopic relation

906. [3]

The Pasting Theorem

907. Theorem

$$\forall x \in A \cup B, f(x) = g(x) \rightarrow h \equiv \text{continuous}$$

908. $(X, \mathcal{T}), (Y, \mathcal{U}) :=$ topological spaces

909. $A, B \subseteq X$; $A, B :=$ closed; $X = A \cup B$

910. $f : A \rightarrow Y$; $g : B \rightarrow Y$; $f, g :=$ continuous

911. $h : X \rightarrow Y$

$$912. h(x) = \begin{cases} f(x), & \text{if } x \in A \\ g(x), & \text{if } x \in B \end{cases}$$

913. [3]

Homotopy is an Equivalence Relation

914. Theorem

\simeq is an equivalence relation

915. $\simeq :=$ homotopic relation

916. [3]

Path Connected

917. Definitions

918.

$$X = [0, 1] \rightarrow f, g := \text{paths}$$

919.

$$a, b \in Y \rightarrow f' := \text{path in } Y \text{ from } a \text{ to } b$$

920.

$$\forall a, b \in Y, \exists f : f \equiv \text{path from } a \text{ to } b \rightarrow (Y, \mathcal{U}) := \text{path connected}$$

921. $(X, \mathcal{T}), (Y, \mathcal{U}) := \text{topological spaces}$

922. $f, g : X \rightarrow Y$

923. $f' : [0, 1] \rightarrow Y$ continuous

924. $a := \text{initial point}$

925. $b := \text{terminal point}$

926. [3]

Convex

927. Definition

$$\forall t \in [0, 1], x, y \in X \rightarrow (1-t)x + ty \in X \Rightarrow (X, \mathcal{T}) := \text{convex}$$

928. Theorem

$$\forall (X, \mathcal{T}) \equiv \text{convex} \rightarrow (X, \mathcal{T}) := \text{path connected}$$

929. $(X, \mathcal{T}) :=$ topological space

930. [3]

Path Homotopy

931. Definitions

932. $F :=$ path homotopy from f to g

$$(i) \quad \forall s \in [0, 1] : F(s, 0) = f(s), \quad F(s, 1) = g(s)$$

$$(ii) \quad \forall t \in [0, 1] : F(0, t) = a, \quad F(1, t) = b$$

933.

$$\exists \text{ path homotopy from } f \text{ to } g \rightarrow f \simeq_p g$$

934. $f, g : [0, 1] \rightarrow Y$; $f, g :=$ continuous functions

935. $a :=$ initial point of f and g

936. $b :=$ terminal point of f and g

937. $F : [0, 1] \times [0, 1] \rightarrow Y$

938. $\simeq_p :=$ path homotopic relation

939. [3]

Path Homotopy is an Equivalence Relation

940. Theorem

\simeq_p is an equivalence relation

941. $\simeq_p :=$ path homotopic relation

942. [3]

Product of Paths

943. Definition

$$(f \star g)(s) := \begin{cases} f(2s), & \text{if } s \in \left[0, \frac{1}{2}\right] \\ g(2s - 1), & \text{if } s \in \left[\frac{1}{2}, 1\right] \end{cases}$$

944. $f :=$ path in Y from a to b

945. $g :=$ path in Y from b to c

946. $f \star g :=$ product of f and $g :=$ path in Y from a to c

947. [3]

Continuous, Paths, Path Homotopy, Composition of Functions

948. Theorem

$(X, \mathcal{T}), (Y, \mathcal{U}) \equiv$ topological spaces,

$h : X \rightarrow Y$ continuous,

$f, g : [0, 1] \rightarrow X \equiv$ paths in X

$F : [0, 1] \times [0, 1] \rightarrow X \equiv$ path homotopy from f to g

\implies

$h \circ f : [0, 1] \times [0, 1] \rightarrow Y \equiv$ path homotopy from $h \circ f$ to $h \circ g$

949. [3]

Well-defined Operation on Path Homotopy Classes

952. Theorem

$$(f \star g)(s) = \begin{cases} f(2s), & \text{if } s \in [0, \frac{1}{2}] \\ g(2s - 1), & \text{if } s \in [\frac{1}{2}, 1] \end{cases}$$

953. $(Y, \mathcal{T}) :=$ topological space

954. $f :=$ path in Y from a to b

955. $g :=$ path in Y from b to c

956. $f \star g :=$ product of f and $g :=$ path in Y from a to c

957. Theorem

$$[f] \bar{\star} [g] = [f \star g]$$

(i) associativity: $[f] \bar{\star} ([g] \bar{\star} [h]) = ([f] \bar{\star} [g]) \bar{\star} [h]$

(ii) left and right identities: $y \in Y, c_y : [0, 1] \rightarrow Y, c_y(s) = y$
 $(f : [0, 1] \rightarrow Y \equiv \text{path in } Y \text{ from } a \text{ to } b) \Rightarrow$
 $\Rightarrow ([c_a] \bar{\star} [f] = [f], [f] \bar{\star} [c_b] = [f])$

(iii) inverse:

$f : [0, 1] \rightarrow Y \equiv \text{path from } a \text{ to } b,$

$\bar{f} : [0, 1] \rightarrow Y, \bar{f}(s) = f(1 - s) \Rightarrow$

$\Rightarrow \bar{f} \equiv \text{path from } b \text{ to } a, [f] \bar{\star} [\bar{f}] = [c_a], [\bar{f}] \bar{\star} [f] = [c_b]$

958. $[f], [g] :=$ homotopy classes

959. $\bar{\star} :=$ well-defined operation on $[f], [g]$

960. \star induces $\bar{\star}$

961. $c_y :=$ constant path

962. [3]

Fundamental Group, Base Point, Loop

963. Definition

loop in Y based at $a :=$ path that begins and ends at a

964. Theorem

$(\pi_1(Y, a), \bar{*}) \equiv$ fundamental group of Y relative to a

965. $\pi_1(Y, a) = \{[f] \mid f := \text{loop based at } a\}$

966. $[f] :=$ path homotopy class of f

967. $a :=$ base point

968. [3]

Path Connected, Isomorphism

969. Theorem

$$(Y, \mathcal{U}) \equiv \text{path connected} \rightarrow \forall a, b \in Y : \pi_1(Y, a) \cong \pi_1(Y, b)$$

970. $(Y, \mathcal{U}) :=$ topological space

971. $\cong :=$ isomorphic relation

972. [3]

Path Components, Equivalence Classes, Path Connected

973. Definitions

974.

$$a \sim b \leftrightarrow \exists \text{ path from } a \text{ to } b$$

975.

path components := equivalence classes of \sim

976. (Y, \mathcal{U}) := topological space

977. \sim is an equivalence relation.

978. *Each equivalence class is path connected.*

979. [3]

Topological Equivalence, Isomorphism, Fundamental Groups

980. Theorem

$$(X, \mathcal{T}) \equiv_t (Y, \mathcal{U}) \rightarrow (G_X \cong G_Y)$$

981. $(X, \mathcal{T}), (Y, \mathcal{U}) :=$ topological spaces

982. $\equiv_t :=$ topological equivalence

983. $\cong :=$ isomorphic relation

984. $G_X, G_Y :=$ fundamental groups

985. [3]

The Fundamental Group of the Circle

986. Theorem

$$G_{\mathbb{S}^1} \cong (\mathbb{Z}, +)$$

987. $G_{\mathbb{S}^1} :=$ fundamental group of \mathbb{S}^1

988. $\cong :=$ isomorphic relation

989. [3]

Lifting

990. Definition

$(h_f : X \rightarrow Z \text{ continuous, } g \circ h_f = f) := \text{lifting of } f$

f lifts to h_f

991. $(X, \mathcal{T}), (Y, \mathcal{U}), (Z, \mathcal{V}) := \text{topological spaces}$

992. $f : X \rightarrow Y; \quad g : Z \rightarrow Y; \quad f, g := \text{continuous functions}$

993. [3]

Standard Covering Map of the Circle

994. Definition

$g :=$ standard covering map of \mathbb{S}^1

995. $g : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{S}^1; \quad g(x) = (\cos 2\pi x, \sin 2\pi x)$

996. g wraps around the unit circle infinitely many times.

997. [3]

Standard Covering Map, Circle, Uniqueness, Lift

998. Theorem

$$\begin{aligned}d(0) = (x, y) \in \mathbb{S}^1, \quad z \in g^{-1}[\{x, y\}] &\Rightarrow \\ \Rightarrow \exists! k_d : [0, 1] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}, \quad k_d(0) = z &\end{aligned}$$

999. $g : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{S}^1; \quad g(x) = (\cos 2\pi x, \sin 2\pi x)$

1000. $g :=$ standard covering map of \mathbb{S}^1

1001. $d : [0, 1] \rightarrow \mathbb{S}^1 :=$ path

1002. $\exists! :=$ there is *exactly* one

1003. $k_d :=$ lift of d

1004. [3]

Retraction

1005. Definition

$(f : X \rightarrow A) := \text{retraction}$ if $(\forall a \in A) f(a) = a$

1006. $f :=$ continuous map

1007. $A \subseteq_s X$

1008. $\subseteq_s :=$ subspace relation

1009. $A :=$ retract of X

1010. [6]

Retract

1011. Definition

$A := \text{retract of } X \text{ if } (\exists f : X \rightarrow X)(\forall x \in X)(\forall a \in A)$

(i) $f(x) \in A$

(ii) $f(a) = a$

1012. $f := \text{retraction}$

1013. $A \subseteq_s X$

1014. $\subseteq_s := \text{subspace relation}$

1015. [6]

Absolute Retract

1016. Definition

$$\begin{aligned} (X \in \mathcal{K}, \forall Y \in \mathcal{K} : X \subseteq Y, X := \text{retract of } Y) &\rightarrow \\ &\rightarrow (X := \text{absolute retract for } \mathcal{K}) \end{aligned}$$

1017. $\mathcal{K} :=$ class of topological spaces closed under homeomorphism

1018. $X :=$ topological space

1019. [6]

Abstract Simplicial Complex

1020. Definition

$(A \in S \rightarrow \forall A' : A' \in S) \rightarrow (S := \text{abstract simplicial complex})$

1021. $S := \text{finite} \neq \emptyset$

1022. $\emptyset \neq A' \subseteq A$

1023. [6]

Open Invitation

Review, add content, and co-author this white paper [7,8].

*Join the **Open Mathematics Collaboration**.*

Send your contribution to `mplobo@uft.edu.br`.

Open Science

The **latex file** for this *white paper* together with other *supplementary files* are available in [9,10].

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Agreement

The author agrees with [8].

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